

Teacher's Role in Developing Elementary School's Student's Literacy

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to determine the role of elementary school teachers in Manggarai in developing literacy culture. This research used observation and interview techniques. The respondents were elementary school teachers in Manggarai. The data analysis used in this study was descriptive qualitative analysis. From the results of observations and interviews, it was found that most of the teachers have implemented reading and writing literacy for 15 minutes before learning begins, used sources and image media to help and facilitate students in understanding the material read and written, guided and trained and guided students directly in reading and writing, created reading and writing habits during the learning process.

INTRODUCTION

The development of science and technology has created a society that continues to strive to improve its abilities in the world of education. One of the efforts to advance education is curriculum innovation. The curriculum has an important role in organizing, directing and transmitting knowledge and guiding learning activities (Longhurtst, 2016., Young, 2004). In Indonesia, in line with curriculum changes in 2013, the government launched the School Literacy Movement (GLS) program which aims to improve student literacy. Furthermore, in 2018 it was upgraded to national literacy, which applies to all levels of society.

Literacy is a fundamental human right in improving life and can achieve personal, social, employment goals open social opportunities and economic and political integration (Rahanu et al., 2016); (Pinto, Boler, & Norris, 2007). UNESCO (2015) explains that literacy is essential for humans for social development and changing lives to improve one's health, one's income and one's relationship with the world.

Literacy culture is a social culture that includes all human endeavors related to reading and writing. The main components of literacy culture are reading, writing and critical thinking activities. This is in line with Mulis' opinion (Septiana & Ibrohim, 2020), currently, it cannot be denied that the progress of education in a country is determined by the literacy culture of its students, because the ability of students to literacy is the initial capital in achieving success in understanding lessons. One indicator of learning success is the better level of student literacy, which is characterized by the better absorption of students in understanding the knowledge gained in a learning process. The essence of literacy is reading-thinking-writing activities (Suyono, 2009). In simple terms, UNESCO defines literacy as a person's ability to read and write. Meanwhile, someone who has skills in literacy is not only limited to the ability to read and write but also the ability to speak, listen, think and use all these abilities to carry out daily activities both in the school environment and outside school.

Literacy culture is closely related to learning patterns in schools and the availability of reading materials in libraries. Literacy culture aims to make a habit of thinking followed by a process of reading, writing which in the end what will be done in a process of activity will create a work. Data from the Progressin International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS) in the field of reading in grade IV elementary school children around the world under the coordination of The International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA) which is followed by 45 countries or states, both from developed and developing countries, the results show that Indonesian students are ranked 41st in the object of reading and writing interest research (PIRLS, 2011).

The School Literacy Movement is a character building movement that aims to equip students with a culture of reading and writing that creates lifelong learning. This is in line with Suragangga (Arianti, 2018) in order to overcome these problems, the Government of the Republic of Indonesia through the Ministry of Education and Culture has launched the School Literacy Movement (GLS) program which aims to: 1) develop a literacy culture of reading and writing in schools, 2) increase the capacity of citizens and the school environment to be aware of the importance of literacy culture, 3) make schools a fun and child-friendly learning garden, and 4) present a variety of reading books and accommodate various reading strategies to support learning sustainability.

The implementation of GLS has three stages, namely, the habituation stage, the development stage, and the learning stage. The habituation stage aims to foster students' interest in reading and in reading activities. Next, the development stage. Literacy activities at the development stage aim to maintain interest in reading and reading activities, as well as improve students' reading

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fluency and comprehension. In the third stage, the learning stage, the purpose of this stage is to maintain students' interest in reading and reading activities and to improve students' literacy skills through enrichment books and textbooks. GLS activities are carried out during the first 15 minutes before the lesson starts. This activity is filled with reading activities (Permen No 37 of 2018).

Permen No.37 Year (2018) literacy aims to strengthen the learning objectives in the Content Standards. All learning events have listening, reading, listening, speaking and writing activities. All learning events use language as the main vehicle for knowledge and skill transfer in addition to non-linguistic symbols (e.g. pictures, photos, videos). All learning also uses logical thinking to complete tasks and express opinions. Thus, literacy skills are fundamental to the success of all subjects. Literacy development should be realized by all teachers. Teachers should implement literacy strategies in every learning process. Literacy strategies include two main things: language skills and thinking skills. It is these two things that are seriously and continuously nurtured in all learning events inside and outside the classroom.

The role of the teacher is not finished with just educating and teaching. Another task of teachers towards students is to guide and direct students to stay on the right track, especially in the teaching and learning process. The role of the teacher has many things, namely as a class coordinator, teacher, mediator, evaluator, lesson planning, director, motivator, providing learning materials / learning resources, facilitator, and managing the learning environment, as well as a model and role model (Rusman, 2014., Muhammad, 2020., Yohana (2020)). In this case, the teacher as a role model for students is very important and must also control students if students' interest in literacy culture is very lacking, therefore the role of a teacher is very necessary. Furthermore, Hidayat (2018) states that the role of the teacher in developing a culture of literacy is how the teacher instructs all students to give assignments to read books at home and how to create programs or activities at school that can support these literacy activities, namely by asking all students to be required to visit the library to read with a set schedule every day. This activity is carried out with the aim of fostering interest in reading and improving reading skills so that students can increase their knowledge and insight.

Based on the results of Susanti's research (2021), on the Role of Teachers in Increasing Reading Interest, teachers play a role as creators in increasing students' interest in reading by creating new activities or ideas in reading. The creations carried out include: (1) holding special reading activities, (2) holding competitions related to reading, (3) asking students to buy reading books, (4) holding activities to visit the library, (5) holding reading activities from online sources, (6) asking students to send recordings of the reading process. The results of this study show that the role of teachers is very important in increasing students' interest in reading.

This type of research is qualitative research. According to Anggito & Setiawan (2018), qualitative research is data collection in a scientific setting with the intention of interpreting the phenomena that occur, where the researcher is the key instrument, sampling of data sources is done purposively and snowbaal, collection techniques (interviews, observation, and documentation) with triangulation (combined), data analysis is inductive / qualitative, and qualitative research results emphasize meaning rather than generalization.

METHODS

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Data collection techniques were interview, documentation study and observation. The researcher was able to interact directly with the research subjects, namely primary school teachers in Manggarai, regarding their role in developing a literacy culture in primary schools.

The data analysis carried out in this research is qualitative descriptive analysis. In this case, the data analysis is more of a description of the results of the interview. The data that has been obtained will be analyzed qualitatively and described in descriptive form. Data analysis carried out in this study using three lines of activity proposed by Miles and Huberman (Sugiyono, 2015) are as follows data reduction, data presentation and conclusion drawing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following are some excerpts of the results of interviews with teachers who teach at elementary schools in Manggarai using several three indicator questions related to reading and writing literacy culture, namely as educators, teachers as mentors, teachers as trainers in reading and writing literacy culture.

1. Teachers as Educators in Developing a Literacy Culture of Reading and Writing

The results of the interview with teacher **A** explained that

I as an educator in developing a literacy culture must be able to instill the attitude or habit of reading and writing into students. The literacy movement in schools, especially in the classroom, is carried out 15 minutes before learning.

Furthermore, the results of the interview with teacher **B** explained that:

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In relation to the culture of literacy, my role is to train, guide and direct students so that they can increase the culture of reading and writing in students by reading literacy for 15 minutes before learning begins.

The same thing was conveyed by teacher **C** and teacher **D**

both said that as an educator my role is to guide, direct and motivate in order to encourage students to be more active in participating in reading and writing literacy activities.

The interview results from several informants above are also supported by observational data related to the role of teachers as educators in developing a literacy culture of reading and writing for students. Before the learning process begins, the teacher directs students to read for 15 minutes before learning begins. In the learning process, teachers always guide students in reading and writing literacy, directing and motivating students to be more active in participating in reading and writing literacy activities.

The role of teachers as educators is to educate, train and provide and transfer knowledge and skills to students. The teacher's role as an educator is to provide and transfer knowledge and skills to students. In the literacy learning process at Manggarai Primary School, the teacher's role is also to train, guide and direct in order to increase the knowledge and skills of students. This is in line with the results of research conducted by Dasem (2018) that the role of the teacher in carrying out the learning process is to function as a manager and director of learning such as lesson planning, implementing learning programs, building good communication with students, taking an individual approach, and innovating learning and evaluation. Literacy activities aim to develop the ability to understand reading and relate it to personal experiences, think critically, and process communication skills creatively through activities to respond to enrichment reading (Purcell-Gates et al, 2012).

2. Teachers as mentors in developing a culture of literacy

Interview results with Teacher **E**

The strategy I use so that students are always concentrated in following the literacy learning process is to use media that is in accordance with the subject matter. For example, asking students to show pictures related to the material or reading text, then asking students to tell about what is in the picture and directing students to the text that has been provided.

Furthermore, the results of the interview with Teacher **F**

In order for students to always concentrate, I always guide, direct and convey the importance of reading and writing literacy to students and use media that is suitable for the material to be taught. So that students can learn easily because they are assisted by various learning resources and media.

The results of interviews from several informants above are also supported by observational data related to the role of the teacher as a mentor in developing a literacy culture of reading and writing to students. In the learning process, the teacher opens the lesson by asking students to look at the pictures in the textbook and read silently related to the content of the text in the picture.

Based on the results of the interviews and observations above, it can be concluded that the strategy or method carried out by the teacher so that students always concentrate in the literacy learning process is to provide media and learning resources that are suitable for developing a literacy culture of reading and writing within students. Using learning media can involve students to train thinking about what they are seeing and being able to retell what they have read. Heinich, et al (1985) explained that learning media serves to provide messages that have a purpose in learning.

One of the strategies of primary school teachers in Manggarai in guiding literacy culture is to provide learning resources and learning media in accordance with the needs and characteristics of students. This is done so that students always concentrate on the learning process. The sources and media prepared by teachers in primary schools in Manggarai are textbooks, reading books that students are interested in, the availability of reading corners and story books. With these media, students can involve themselves to see and think about what they are seeing and be able to tell others. This is in line with Safitri (2021), that teachers guide students in finding the right reading books, a reading corner is provided in each class in order to foster interest in reading in students. The teacher as a coach. This is in line with Gagne and Brigs (1974) that learning media includes tools that can physically be used to convey the content of teaching materials such as books, videos, films, slides, pictures, photos, recorders, computers and so on.

Interview result with Teacher **G**

As a low-grade teacher, I always guide and train students in reading and writing. Students who are not yet fluent in reading and writing can become fluent because they are accustomed to reading and writing activities through literacy activities.

Furthermore, an interview with teacher informant **H**

Many things are obtained by students after participating in literacy activities. Both knowledge and skills and have a positive impact on changes in student attitudes and behavior. For example, increasing knowledge, communication skills, writing skills, and students who have not read fluently will become fluent.

Based on the results of the interviews and observations above, it can be concluded that the teacher's role is to guide and train students in reading and writing. The existence of media and learning resources, students more easily understand and appreciate the material that has been explained. So that it can increase knowledge both writing skills and skills to communicate. In addition, the positive impact obtained by students is a change in attitude and behavior.

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Teachers as trainers carry out their role by training students in the formation of basic competencies in accordance with the potential of each student. In terms of literacy culture, primary school teachers in Manggarai act as trainers by guiding, directing, training, and encouraging students.

From the three interview indicators above, primary school teachers in Manggarai have carried out their role in developing a literacy culture. This is in accordance with Solikhan's (2015) opinion that literacy is defined as the ability to read and write. Reading and writing literacy at primary schools in Manggarai requires appropriate strategies from teachers and preparation of learning resources and media used as intermediaries in understanding what is read and written. Perry & Homan (2014) explain that literacy involves contextual aspects, more actions and is connected to the formation of attitudes, values, feelings.

CONCLUSION

Literacy in elementary school students is part of a social culture that can create a pattern of habituation. This pattern will give birth to meaningful understanding for students. This can be realized through the role of teachers in developing and implementing learning strategies. In this regard, primary school teachers in Manggarai have carried out their roles well, through their roles as educators, mentors and trainers. These three roles are reflected in the process of literacy activities that have been practiced through 15-minute activities before learning begins. Furthermore, reading and writing habituation is also carried out during the learning process. In addition, teachers also use resources and image media in reading and writing literacy to help facilitate students in practicing reading and writing.

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